

“Poincaré’s classification of hypotheses and their role in natural science”

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Abstract *In the Introduction of his famous book *La Science et l’Hypothèse*, Poincaré remarks the necessary role and legitimacy of hypotheses. There, he establishes a triple classification of hypotheses, dividing them in verifiable, useful, and apparent. However, in Chapter IX of the same book, entitled “*Les hypothèses en Physique*”, he gives a slightly different triadic classification: natural hypotheses, indifferent hypotheses, and real generalizations. The origin of this second classification is in a lecture given in the International Congress of Physics which took place in Paris in 1900. What are the similarities and differences between these two classifications? My main purpose is to provide a possible equivalence between both classifications in order to clarify the role of hypothesis in Poincaré’s epistemology of natural science. The discussion will be based in the two fundamental texts above quoted and in the contrast of Poincaré’s use of this notion (hypothesis) with some of his contemporaries.*

The role of hypothesis in Poincaré’s philosophy has been stated by himself and also by his commentators on several places (Heinzmann 2009; Walter 2009; Walter 2010; Ly 2008; Zahar 2001). He considers that hypotheses are essential for the constitution and development of science (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 23-24). Hypotheses are the first step to constitute a scientific theory, and in this sense, also scientific knowledge. To Poincaré, hypotheses only take place in geometry and physics, and not in arithmetic. We are here dealing only with hypothesis in natural science, that is, physics and mechanics, because hypothesis in geometry correspond to geometrical axioms or conventions as stated since Poincaré’s first considerations on the topic (Poincaré 1881, p. 773).

However important it is, the concept of hypothesis seems to be difficult to clarify since Poincaré distinguishes different kinds of them. In a gap of two years he publishes two different typologies of hypotheses, one in 1900 and the other in 1902. These two classifications are apparently not equivalent. In order to provide a clarification of Poincaré’s

notion of hypothesis, our aim here is to compare and to bring to light a possible equivalence between these two typologies.

In 1902, in the Introduction of his famous book *Science and Hypothesis* he presents the following triadic classification:

We shall also see that there are several kinds of hypothesis; that some are verifiable, and when once confirmed by experiment become truths of great fertility; that others may be useful to us in fixing our ideas; and finally, that others are hypotheses only in appearance, and reduce to definitions or to conventions in disguise. The latter are to be met with especially in mathematics and in the sciences to which it is applied. From them, indeed, the sciences derive their rigour (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 24).

So, as a starting point we can talk about verifiable, useful, and apparent hypotheses. Our problem begins when we look at chapter IX of the same book and we find a slightly different triadic classification:

We must also take care to distinguish between the different kinds of hypothesis. First of all, there are those which are quite natural and necessary. It is difficult not to suppose that the influence of very distant bodies is quite negligible, that small movements obey a linear law, and that effect is a continuous function of its cause. I will say as much for the conditions imposed by symmetry. All these hypotheses affirm, so to speak, the common basis of all the theories of mathematical physics. They are the last that should be abandoned. There is a second category of hypotheses which I shall qualify as indifferent. In most questions the analyst assumes, at the beginning of his calculations, either that matter is continuous, or the reverse, that it is formed of atoms. In either case, his results would have been the same. [...] If, the experiment confirms his conclusions, will he suppose that he has proved, for example, the real existence of atoms? [...]

These indifferent hypotheses are never dangerous provided their characters are not misunderstood. They may be useful, either as artifices for calculation, or to assist our understanding by concrete images, to fix the ideas, as we say. They need not therefore to be rejected. The hypotheses of the third category are real generalizations. They must be confirmed or invalidated by experiment. Whether verified or condemned, they will always be fruitful; but, for the reasons I have given, they will only be so if they are not too numerous (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p.166-167).

As a result, in this second classification we have a distinction between natural hypotheses, indifferent hypotheses, and hypotheses as real generalizations. The origin of this second classification is in a lecture given in the International Congress of Physics which took place in Paris in 1900.

In order to fulfil our aim, we start with the analysis of the second kind of hypotheses in both typologies, that is, “useful hypothesis” in the first one and “indifferent hypothesis” in the second one. These two kinds of hypothesis seem to be easily identifiable. Indeed, regarding to “indifferent hypothesis”, in chapter X, Poincaré states:

Hypotheses of this kind have therefore only a metaphorical sense. The scientist should no more banish them than a poet banishes a metaphor; but he ought to know what they are worth. They may be useful to give satisfaction to the mind, and they will do no harm as long as they are only indifferent hypothesis (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 176).

Hence, in our attempt to assimilate the two typologies, we can see that the second kind of hypothesis can be identified as the same kind in both. They are useful in the sense that they have an explanative role for us, but they cannot be considered either true or false. Indifferent hypothesis can be also interpreted as “conventions freely invented by the mind” as has been done by Giedymin (1982, p. VIII) and other commentators (Heinzmann 2009, p. 174). In this sense, “convention” could be understood as a suitable agreement. An agreement regarding, for example, the convenience of using one mechanical model better than another, or the convenience of accepting atoms instead of continuous matter for the purpose of some calculations. However, this kind of convention is not the same as the conventions stated in the first typology, I mean, the disguised definitions. From my point of view, that is the reason why Poincaré takes care in distinguishing them. Conventions in the first typology are epistemologically relevant, and indifferent hypotheses are called as such, that is, indifferent, because their adoption does not modify essential points in the structure of a theory or in its epistemological value. By ‘epistemologically relevant’ I mean conventions that make a difference in physical theory, indeed if we change them we get a different theory, and that is not the case with indifferent hypothesis.¹ As a result, the choice of an indifferent hypothesis depends on its convenience and on its heuristic value for the explanation of the theory. So, they are not chosen in a completely arbitrary way, but they are indifferent regarding the

epistemological content. In any case, these hypotheses make statements about the ontology of a theory and therefore, physics is not concerned by them, but only metaphysics.

Furthermore, Poincaré is not the only scientist who stresses the existence of these useful hypotheses. When Boltzmann speaks of hypotheses as “arbitrary pictures” (Boltzmann 1904, p. 593) we can identify these ones with Poincaré’s indifferent hypothesis. Boltzmann defines these hypotheses as the ones that “give the imagination room for play and by boldly going beyond the material at hand” (Boltzmann 1904, p. 593). The proof of this equivalence is one of the examples used by both, that is, the ether. Boltzmann characterizes the elastic ether as a hypothesis of this kind, a hypothesis subject to change, but one that provides us with a picture of the “representation of the phenomena of interference and refraction of light” (Boltzmann 1904, p. 593). On the other hand, Poincaré says: “Whether the ether exists or not matters little –let us leave that to the metaphysicians, what is essential for us is, that everything happens as if it existed, and that this hypothesis is found to be suitable for the explanation of phenomena” (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 215). That is why Poincaré says that indifferent hypotheses have only a metaphorical sense.

Continuing with the analysis of the typologies, we look now at verifiable hypothesis as described in the text of the Introduction. Here, ‘verifiable’ means that can be proved by experiment. These hypotheses are the ones that fit better with the common use of the word ‘hypothesis’, that is, a provisional supposition taken as a basis for a further research which will confirm or refute that hypothesis. In general, when a hypothesis is confirmed it becomes predictive, that is, it can announce future events based on an empirical ground. As Poincaré says, “a hypothesis is more plausible when it explains new facts” (Poincaré 1913, p. 82). Thus, it is easy to make the equivalence between this kind and hypotheses as “real generalizations” quoted in chapter IX. Truly, Poincaré did not explicitly assert that verifiable hypothesis were inductive generalizations of empirical facts. But these generalizations, once confirmed, become fruitful because of their ability to predict. So, no other kind of hypothesis could fit with this kind, taking into account that they share the features of (1) ability of confirmation by experiment and (2) making fruitful predictions of new facts.

Moreover, we can identify these generalizations as genuine hypothesis,² opposite to others that are indifferent or just apparent hypothesis. These are the ones that have to be submitted to empirical verification and they must be abandoned if their predictions are not fulfilled. The significance of this hypothesis becomes clear when we seek for similarities within the perspectives of some of Poincaré’s contemporaries. Helmholtz also considers inductive generalizations based in a collection of facts as hypotheses (Helmholtz [1862]

1995, p. 90). To him, these hypotheses help us to find the invariant laws of nature. They are the guide to find the right path, the first step in order to discover the knowledge of nature. To Poincaré, these hypotheses, once confirmed, become experimental laws. In the same way, John Stuart Mill states that inductive generalizations are suggested by observation and they start as hypothesis (Mill [1843] 1976, p. 432). Once confirmed, they will become laws. Even Mach, despite his critics to Mill's inductivism, explains hypothesis in natural science as a process of backwards inference which starts with "the given facts", to something which is not defined (Mach [1905] 1976, p. 173). That is, a hypothesis, to Mach, is a possibility stated in a process of backwards inference, and it is constituted as something provisional (Mach [1905] 1976, p. 178) which is a support to the understanding of a set of facts. Hence, a hypothesis is a kind of conjecture that helps us to compose something that we do not know yet, from something that we *do* know, that is, from the facts. Moreover, hypotheses have the specific ability to conceive new facts, and there, is when they prove their value. As we can see, that is quite similar with the ability of prediction or with fruitful hypotheses in Poincaré's sense.

As a result, we have established two equivalences between the two typologies. The trouble is now to see the possible relation, if any, between conventions in the first classification and natural hypothesis in the second one. If we remember the definition of both, in the text of the introduction, regarding conventions, Poincaré says that they "are to be met with especially in mathematics and in the sciences to which it is applied. From them, indeed, the sciences derive their rigour" (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 24). On the other hand, in chapter IX, concerning natural hypothesis, he states that they "affirm the common basis of all the theories of mathematical physics" (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 166). This is, at first sight, the only common point of these two kinds of hypothesis since 'mathematical physics' is a science to which mathematics is applied. Although it might appear as not being enough, this is the core of our proof for the possible equivalence of both typologies.

It has been stated that natural hypothesis "may have folded in the category of generalizations" (Walter 2009, p. 202). The reason to this reduction of natural hypothesis to verifiable hypothesis is that both seem, in principle, to be accessible to experiment. If this were the case, this would amount to the suppression of natural hypothesis in the 1902 typology. Poincaré does not assert that these hypotheses are verifiable, but we could understand so, deriving from the kind of examples he gives, such as: to neglect the influence of very distant bodies, or to consider movements as linear. These are no doubt examples taken from experience or from empirical consideration. As these examples may be refuted by experience, they could be understood as verifiable hypothesis and, as such, they could be

rejected if they are no longer true. But from my point of view, they have a different purpose than empirical generalizations. They are practical rules that help us to constitute our theories of mathematical physics. They are taken from experience but our aim is not to verify them but to use them to construct empirical laws. Such is the case of the examples provided by Poincaré: the influence of very distant bodies is quite negligible, small movements obey a linear law, and effect is a continuous function of its cause (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 166).

This last example, that “effect is a continuous function of its cause” is defined in *La Valeur de la Science* (Poincaré [1905] 1970, p. 176-177)³ as the principle of induction with this statement: “When the same antecedent recurs, the same consequent must likewise recur”. The relation between an antecedent producing a consequent is the same as the relation between a cause producing an effect or an effect *being a continuous function of its cause*, as Poincaré states in *Science and Hypothesis*. We name this principle as “the principle of physical induction” rather than only “the principle of induction” (as it is literally named by Poincaré) in order to distinguish it from the “principle of complete induction” which is so important in Poincaré’s philosophy of arithmetic, and which he defines as a synthetic a priori judgment (Poincaré [1908] 1999, p. 30).⁴ Thus, the principle of physical induction is necessary in order to make any empirical generalization and of course it could be verifiable and it could be proven to be false, but that is not the status that we give to it. We use it as if it were always true. So, natural hypotheses are not falsable regarding the use that we make of them.

With this last claim, conventions come close to natural hypothesis. Conventions in natural science are usually interpreted by Poincaré as principles, especially as mechanical principles (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 128). They are inspired by experimental laws, that is, generalizations, and transformed into conventions by the use that we make of them, guided by convenience and simplicity. It is we who take them to their conventional status. We consider them as not verifiable and we extend their domain of application to the whole universe not submitting them to experimental proof (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 151). So, conventions are experimental laws taken by our decision and our choice to a higher status where they are no more empirically verifiable. So, if we stress our role of decision in science, that is, the use we give to some scientific statements, we can see a rapprochement between natural hypothesis and conventions. What I mean is that we decide the non verifiable status of these two notions.

Hence, we have a characterization of natural hypothesis as principles required to construct empirical generalizations. It has been stated that as such, these hypotheses may be

conditions for science inaccessible to experiment (Heinzmann 2009, p. 174). However, as it has been showed before, looking at the examples that Poincaré himself provides, this is not the case, strictly speaking, because these examples are obtained from experience. They have also been characterized as practical rules not falsable from the perspective of theoretical construction (Walter 2010, p. 133), and that is exactly the point that we wanted to remark before. Natural hypothesis are practical rules taken from experience but not falsifiable by it, that help us in constructing our laws and theories; that help us, therefore, in constructing our science.

At this point, we can say that they work as regulative laws for scientific practice, or regulative principles as it has also been pointed out (Ly 2008, p. 611). By this we mean that they are heuristic rules that guide us in the systematization of our theories, because they help us in unifying phenomena to make generalizations. So, they can be understood in the Kantian sense of “rules according to which a unity of experiences may arise from perception” (Kant [1787] 1929, p. 222), because this rules guide us in putting together some similar phenomena to construct generalizations. Although they cannot be considered Kantian in the sense that regulative principles are a priori rules, because they are inspired by experience. By working as rules that regulate scientific method, it is clear that they form the common basis of physical theories. They help us to construct those theories; we use them to construct our generalizations. Hence, they can be distinguished from conventions as mechanical principles, because as regulative principles they have to exist *before* the constitution of a theory, even before the constitution of a law. Conventions understood as principles of mechanics can be made only *after* the constitution of scientific laws, from where they take their experimental basis. Only after the existence of a law, can a convention be stated as such, that is, taken to its status of a non verifiable principle. So, the distance between natural hypothesis and convention has increased. This distance is based on the temporal, or better, on the logical order of forming a theory, and also in taking the word ‘convention’ in a univocal sense. It is well known that Poincaré does not always speak about convention in the same sense⁵. Therefore, if we appeal to the polysemy of the word, we will be able to fill the gap between natural hypothesis and conventions.

In order to not open an indefinite field, we want to restrict ourselves to conventions with an epistemological value in Poincaré’s philosophy. As a result, indifferent hypotheses considered as arbitrary or heuristic conventions are left outside of this meaning of convention since, as we showed before, they do not have an epistemological value, but only a

metaphysical or metaphorical one (Heinzmann 2009, p. 174). Thus, we can characterize epistemological conventions as having the following features:

- 1) They have an empirical origin.
- 2) They are not empirically verifiable.
- 3) They help us in the construction of scientific theories.
- 4) They serve as rules for scientific practice.
- 5) They could be demoted if they are no longer useful for prediction.
- 6) They should be the last to be abandoned (we are reluctant to abandon them).
- 7) They should help in our knowledge of the world if we take science as a way of knowledge.

In order to show that natural hypotheses fit with this characterization of epistemological conventions and that principles of mechanics as conventions do so, we are going to take three examples of them (two of natural hypothesis and one of principles of mechanics), given by Poincaré himself, and analyze if they fit with these seven features. As a natural hypothesis we will take the principle of physical induction and the idea that the influence of very distant bodies is quite negligible, and as a mechanical convention we will take the Galilean principle of relative motion.

I am starting with the principle of physical induction. It is defined by Poincaré as I quoted before: “effect is a continuous function of its cause” (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 166). Regarding this, we can say that: (1) it has been inspired by experience in the sense that we take the common elements from several experiences, to compare them to other similar elements, in order to make the inference of a law based in these common elements. (2) As we have said, by the use we make of this principle it becomes unfalsifiable. We use it as if it were true, so it does not need to be verified, now that we have taken it to be true. (3) It helps in constructing generalizations, that is laws; and from laws we construct scientific theories. (4) It is a rule that works to construct generalizations. (5) As a practical rule, we could stop using induction if it would be no longer useful for prediction of new facts. (6) Taking history of science into account, as induction has been useful to make predictions in several cases, we will be reluctant to abandon it and only if it has proven to be useless and harmful for science, we will be willing to dispose of it. (7) As the principle of physical induction helps us to discover laws that express true relations among facts, we have no doubt that it helps in improving our knowledge of the world, if we take for granted that scientific theories do so. As a result, we have shown the case of a natural hypothesis which is an epistemological convention.

We will consider at this point the other example of natural hypothesis: “the influence of very distant bodies is quite negligible” (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 166). Concerning this hypothesis we see that: (1) it has been taken from experience, in the sense that, for example, when we calculate the trajectory of a body in the Solar System, we see that the path followed by the body is not very influenced by bodies situated at thousands of light years of distance. (2) As in the principle of induction, we take this hypothesis as true, that is, we decide its true status. As a result, it is not empirically verifiable, because of the use that we make of it. (3) A hypothesis such as this one helps to construct the universal law of gravitation and also Newtonian Mechanics. (4) It is used as a rule to calculate the trajectories of two celestial bodies which are not very far from each other. (5) When we take into account the theory of astronomical perturbations or if we want to study complex topics such as the stability of the Solar System we see that we have to consider the influence of more distant bodies than the ones we consider by using only the law of gravitation in order to predict these perturbations. So, in that case, we would stop using this practical rule. (6) Concerning the laws of displacements of celestial bodies, we can observe that this rule has always been useful to predict phenomena like eclipses or the path of very eccentric bodies such as comets. Besides, given that this rule simplifies the calculations, we will be reluctant to abandon it. (7) As far as this hypothesis has helped in constructing Newtonian Mechanics and as far as this theory has established true relations between facts, this hypothesis has helped in improving our knowledge of the world. Accordingly, we have found a second example of natural hypothesis that fits with our seven criteria of epistemological convention.

Now, we will see if the principles of mechanics understood as conventions fit also with epistemological conventions. The principle of relative motion is defined as follows: “The movement of any system whatever ought to obey the same laws, whether it is referred to fixed axes or to movable axes which are implied in uniform motion in a straight line” (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 129). If we analyze it we see that: (1) the principle of relative motion is deduced from our inability to observe experimentally an absolute reference frame. (2) As its domain of application is extended to the whole universe it is no longer falsable. (3) It has helped to construct scientific theories such as Newtonian mechanics. (4) When the principle of relative motion is considered as a convention, it becomes a rule for scientific action because it guides our next steps in constructing a theory. That is, when it is considered as applicable to the whole universe, it becomes a rule to support subsequent developments in our theory, such as the Galilean transformations used to describe the same phenomena in different inertial frames. (5) As it is only applicable to inertial frames, it cannot explain

accelerated motion, so when we wanted to apply it to this kind of motion, it would become no longer useful to predict new facts, and it would have to be demoted or substituted for a more general one. (6) The idea of a physics of principles shows Poincaré's reluctance to reject the principles of classical mechanics, and as such, the principle of relative motion. As a result, he would propose the new mechanics in which he tries to make the conjunction between electromagnetism and the classical principle of relativity, by changing Galilean transformations for Lorentz's ones. (7) As long as Newtonian theory has established true relations between facts, and as long as it is applicable to a part of nature, the principle of relative motion, as a principle of classical mechanics, has helped us in improving our knowledge of the world. Consequently, we can consider mechanical principles as epistemological conventions in the sense stated before.

Therefore, we have shown that natural hypotheses are a kind of conventions, that is, epistemological conventions, as we have done for principles of mechanics. However, taking into account the polysemy of the word convention, and although both are epistemological conventions, we do not want to state that natural hypotheses are mechanical principles. As we said before, there is a logical priority in the constitution of natural hypotheses as being the ground to make generalizations. That logical order is important in the constitution of scientific theories and there, is where we state the difference between both classifications of hypotheses. Natural hypotheses are conventions but not every convention is a natural hypothesis. Principles of mechanics are not natural hypotheses because they are constituted as conventions in a different moment of the constitution of science. Thus, natural hypotheses are conventions that constitute the point of depart for empirical laws. And mechanical principles are conventions constituted from empirical laws as a point of depart.

Accordingly, natural hypotheses are not missing in the 1902 typology. They are included as conventions. As a result, the typology of the introduction is broader in its scope. As conventions, we can include the axioms of geometry, the principles of mechanics, and as we have shown, natural hypotheses. We think that the reason that they are not distinguished in that typology is because it appears at the beginning of the book, where Poincaré is trying to describe the whole contents of that work, and he is only telling the grounds of his theory for constituting science but not detailing their particular use regarding each science. He wants to state the significance of conventions in science by asserting the creative role of the mind. Geometrical conventions are to be met in mathematics and from them, geometry derives its rigour. Mechanical principles are to be met in mechanics, which is a science where mathematics is applied. Classical mechanics derives its rigour from the principles of

mechanics adopted as conventions. Natural hypotheses are to be met in mathematical physics and also in mechanics; both are sciences where mathematics is applied. They help us to construct experimental laws that will become conventions. They are the basis to get rigour in mathematical physics.

We can now make a conjecture of why conventions do not appear as such in the second typology. As we said, that typology was first published in 1900 in a paper entitled “The relations between experimental physics and mathematical physics” (Poincaré 1900). As the title points out, the whole paper is related to physics and not to geometry and mechanics, even if Poincaré uses some mechanical examples in some sections. By 1900, Poincaré had a completely developed theory of convention regarding geometry and mechanics, but we think that it was not the same regarding physics. To him, physics includes thermodynamics, the kinetic theory of gases, and his hobbyhorse in this paper, which is electromagnetism. Conventions can be applied to thermodynamics since at least two of its fundamental principles are identified in Poincaré’s ‘physics of principles’ and erected to that status (Poincaré [1905] 1970, pp. 129-130). Besides, by the use of statistical mechanics, the phenomena of heat can be explained by molecular movements which imply mechanization. So, he applied his conventional views to this physical domain but not to the whole physical domain. That is why we state that by 1900 he had not a complete theory of convention regarding physics. None of the principles of this physical program are applicable without problem to the domains of electromagnetism, electrodynamics and electromagnetic optics, or in other words, to Lorentz’s electromagnetic theory⁶.

The problems with electromagnetism can be noted in his analysis of Lorentz’s theory, which he considers a good theory, that is, a theory which expresses true relations. But Poincaré believes that this theory is not yet a complete theory, so he cannot state the conventional status of physical principles. However, natural hypotheses in our perspective are not physical principles. Physical principles, in Poincaré’s view are based on mechanical principles and extended to physical phenomena. Such is the case of the principle of relative motion, that he extended its domain of application to Lorentz’s electromagnetic theory. As we showed before, natural hypotheses cannot be understood as mechanical principles or disguised definitions. Now we claim that natural hypotheses are not physical principles because the way in which Poincaré constructs physical principles is the same as for mechanical principles, they are conventions that do not have the logical priority in the formation of the theory that natural hypotheses do have.

Poincaré does not use the word “convention” in the whole 1900 text. And I think that at that moment, it is because Poincaré wanted to distinguish mechanics from physics. So, from my point of view, Poincaré is trying to not use the word convention in order to avoid a misunderstanding with mechanical principles. He cares for distinguishing the status of mechanics as a well constructed science, which follows the mathematical model given by celestial mechanics; from the status of a rising science, such as physics, whose fundamental principles have not been established yet. He cares also for distinguishing natural hypotheses from the other kinds of conventions such as geometrical and mechanical ones. And he is not intending to show here the role of convention in science as he is doing in the text of the introduction. He aims to distinguish different kinds of hypotheses which we use at different levels of physics, with different domains of application in physics; whereas in the other text, he wants to show the use of hypotheses in all the sciences and not only in physics.

In order to complete the typologies, it must be pointed that before presenting his typology in the 1900 text, Poincaré states that there are some ‘dangerous hypotheses’, that is, those which are tacit and unconscious (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 166). But he also says that mathematical physics compels us to make explicit every hypothesis. As a result, once this science is acting (once mathematical physics is working), there are no more dangerous hypotheses, because it makes them explicit by distinguishing them in the three kinds that he describes immediately after.

In the same spirit, Duhem states that to constitute a physical theory, hypotheses must be made explicit, restricted and detailed (Duhem [1905] 1992, p. 99). However, Poincaré’s and Duhem’s conceptions of hypothesis and of physical theory are significantly different. As one of our aims here is to clarify Poincaré’s conception of hypothesis in contrast with some of his contemporaries, I will briefly consider Duhem’s position in two specific points: the role of mathematics in physics and the part played by hypothesis in the constitution of a theory.

The first one is relevant because mathematics is fundamental to physics, according to Poincaré. In fact, it provides the physicist with “the only language that he can speak” (Poincaré [1905] 1970, p. 105). As Heinzmann states, the term ‘hypothesis’ reveals methodological analogies concerning the process of understanding in mathematics and in physics (Heinzmann 2009, p. 169). Heinzmann establishes an analogy between the use of the principle of recurrence in arithmetic, also known as the principle of complete induction and the principle of physical induction in physical sciences. This shows a correlation between the genesis of mathematical knowledge and the genesis of physical knowledge. This analogy

affects mainly the role of mathematics in hypothesis as generalizations, the second type we have analyzed here. Also, regarding natural hypothesis, Ly explains that they create a link between mathematics and physics, by enabling the use of the infinitesimal calculus (Ly 2008, p. 607), as in the case of the neglect of very distant bodies to calculate trajectories in the solar system. But in a more general way, the idea that mathematics is the only language that physicists can talk is not only relevant for this or that kind of hypothesis or even for the distinction of different kinds of hypotheses (for example, it has not been proved that mathematics plays a determinant role in the formation or selection of indifferent hypothesis), but it is relevant to Poincaré's understanding of physical science. Mathematics, indeed, determines the form of the laws of physics: they are differential equations. Mathematics determines also the form of expression of physical knowledge: the relations contained in theories are expressed in the form of differential equations. Mathematics is the language that allows us for getting rid of the substantialist character of ordinary language, to express in a rigorous way empirical data. Thanks to mathematics, we can get rid of the particularities of singular events to express generalizations and the relations among facts.

The methodological analogies that can be established between physics and mathematics and the fundamental role played by this science to Poincaré are in striking contrast with the position held by Duhem:

We have seen in many respects, how it is dangerous to establish a rapprochement between the mathematical method and the method employed in physical theories. We have seen how, under the appearance of a similarity due to the borrowing of mathematical language by physics, these two sciences are entirely different (Duhem [1906] 1989, p. 404).

Indeed, Duhem denounces the idea of teaching physics by trying to show that hypotheses are proved one after the other, because it gives a false appearance of similitude with geometrical theorems, and this is dangerous because it creates a dogmatic attitude as if the theories have been proved once and forever (Duhem [1906] 1989, pp. 409-410). So, to Duhem, the use of mathematics could lead us to a dogmatic attitude towards science, by creating false analogies with mathematical sciences, such as geometry; whereas to Poincaré, mathematics gives the physicist the best way of articulating his ideas, the most rigorous one. Of course this does not mean that Poincaré defends a dogmatic attitude, because according to him, the certitudes of mechanics as a natural and as an experimental science cannot be

compared to the certitudes of geometry (Poincaré [1902] 1968, p. 153) as a pure mathematical science.

Regarding the second point, that is, the role of hypothesis to Duhem, first of all, we have to consider the position they have in the formation of a theory. According to Duhem, theories are constituted in four successive steps: definition of concepts and magnitudes, choice of hypothesis, mathematical development and comparison between theory and experience (Duhem [1906] 1989, p. 24-25). In the first one a correspondence between certain physical properties and certain magnitudes which are mathematical symbols is established. The relation between symbols and physical properties is strictly symbolical and does not imply a correspondence to nature. Then, the physicist provides a link among the different magnitudes by formulating hypothesis in an arbitrary way, restricted only by the principle of non-contradiction. In the third step, hypotheses are combined according to the rules of mathematical analysis leading to exact calculations. Finally, the consequences extracted from the hypotheses have to be compared with the experimental laws that the theory tries to represent. This is when the theory is submitted to experimental control. Thus, to Duhem, experimental verifications are not the basis of the theory, they are its crowning moment (Duhem [1906] 1988, p. 311).

But how exactly takes place the experimental control? In the duhemian conception of theory, the experimental laws cannot be used before they are interpreted. This implies that there is no possibility of expressing a pure experimental fact because all are theory-laden. An experiment consists not only in the observation of some phenomena, but also in their interpretation. The theoretical interpretation penetrates experience since the very moment in which the physicist tries to account for an experiment in a specific system of symbols. Accordingly, the creation of a language is the creation of the theory itself (Duhem [1906] 1989, p. 228). There are not non-interpreted data. To use experimental laws, the physicist has to be integrated in a certain theoretical conception that provides the interpretation of data, so the only way of submitting the theory to experimental control, is comparing the whole theoretical system with the set of experimental laws. This is the famous holistic thesis, which implies that it is impossible to prove isolated assertions within a theory, because particular statements lose their meaning outside the theory.

Of course, the holistic thesis is a criticism to the inductive method and to the idea of empirical generalizations. There is no possibility of generalizing facts without a previous theory, because induction is useless when observation is theory-laden. Furthermore, generalizations cannot be isolatedly proven. This is completely opposed to Poincaré's

conception. Regarding the structure of a theory, the basis to Poincaré are the empirical facts, which the scientist translates into scientific facts by means of scientific language. But the use of the language does not imply the creation of the facts: the facts remain external to the theory. The language is not a transformation of the facts, but an adequate and convenient way of expression. However, to Duhem, as there is no possibility of observing without lading the observation, this modifies the experimental character of facts, making the theory a language without external referents. The possibility of experimental control is much more present in the process of the constitution of a theory to Poincaré. The role of induction and of empirical generalizations is essential, as we have shown. Besides, there is no arbitrary choice of hypothesis in Poincaré: even indifferent hypotheses are chosen by its convenience.

Despite all these differences, Duhem and Poincaré share a common idea: both of them stress the role of the scientist in the constitution of a theory. That is why Duhem repeatedly emphasizes the role of theory (as in the idea that observations are theory-laden or in the holistic thesis) and that is why Poincaré stresses the role of conventions as freely but non arbitrary decisions taken by the scientist to make a theory more convenient.

To conclude, and going back to Poincaré's classifications of hypothesis, I would like to insist on the common point of both texts. That is, to show the essential position that hypotheses *do* have in science, whether it is concerning science in general or in particular, such as physics. This could be explained as a response to classical positivism that considers a hypothesis as something that we have to avoid. To Comte (1830-1842, t. 1, 28th lecture), hypothesis has an explanatory role, and positive science has to be descriptive and not explicative. Thus, to classical positivism, hypothesis is something that has to disappear when science attains its most perfect level. On the contrary, to Poincaré, hypotheses are something that goes beyond this limited "positive" conception. They are legitimate and necessary for the constitution of science. As Brenner says, "When Poincaré defines three kinds of hypothesis he reacts against a whole tradition which tries to minimize the role of hypothesis. His originality consists of pointing at the existence of other hypotheses than real generalizations: indifferent hypotheses and especially natural hypothesis" (Brenner, 2003, p. 30).

Acknowledgements

I am very grateful to David Stump and Fillipe Varela for insightful comments. I am also indebted to the editor of this journal and the anonymous referees for their contribution. I also thank FCT (Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia) for a PhD grant (SFRH/BD/4478/2008), during which part of this work was done at the Centre for Philosophy of Science at Lisbon University (CFCUL). I am indebted to the Institute of Mathematics at the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ), to PEMat post-graduate program (Programa de Ensino e História da Matemática e da Física), and to CAPES (Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Ensino Superior)

for a post-doctoral fellowship during which I finished this work. I would like also to refer my current institution, Department of Philosophy, Logic and Philosophy of Science of the University of Sevilla and the research project “The Genesis of Mathematical Knowledge: Cognition, History and Practices” (P12-HUM-1216).

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¹ I owe this remark to David Stump.

² Poincaré states that "every generalization is a hypothesis" (Poincaré 1902, p. 165).

³ The origin of this text is in a paper published in 1902 entitled "On the objective value of science". On the identification of this principle with the principle of physical induction, cf. also Heinzmann 2009, p. 184.

⁴ This principle is mainly used for Arithmetic and since it is not a hypothesis we are not going to discuss it.

⁵ For example, Poincaré refers to the difference between conventions in geometry and conventions in mechanics in Poincaré [1902] 1968, pp. 152-153. In fact, Poincaré never had to consider suspending a geometrical convention in the light of new experimental results. However, he reconsidered the classical principle of relative motion in the light of electromagnetism. A discussion of several different senses of the use of 'convention' in Poincaré is in Heinzmann 2010 and also in de Paz 2014.

⁶ Friedman also considers genuinely physical disciplines (namely, electromagnetism) "to be non-conventional". Cf. Friedman 1996, p. 336.